

Volumetric, viscometric and ultrasonic studies of some nitrate compounds in aqueous binary mixture of tetrahydrofuran at various temperatures

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The densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities of NH_4NO_3 , KNO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in a 20 mass% tetrahydrofuran + water mixture have been measured at 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K. Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ), viscosity B -coefficients and adiabatic compressibility of these electrolyte solutions are derived from these data supplemented with their densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities respectively. The limiting apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ^0) and experimental slopes (S_v^*) obtained from the Masson equation have been interpreted in terms of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions, respectively. The viscosity data have been analyzed using the Jones-Dole equation. The results show that these electrolytes have structure breaking capacities in this solvent-mixture. The compressibility data also indicate the electrostriction of solvent molecules around the metal ions.

In continuation of the work¹⁻³ on the classical nature of solutes and their mutual and specific interactions with the solvent molecules, we report here in the density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity measurements in a 20 mass% tetrahydrofuran (THF) + water mixture of ammonium nitrate, potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate as a function of temperature. The nature of various types of interactions prevailing in these electrolyte solutions are also discussed.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) of liquid solutions was calculated from the relation,

$$V_\phi = M/\rho_0 - 1000(\rho - \rho_0)/c\rho_0 \quad (1)$$

where c is the molarity of the solution and the other symbols have their usual significance. The correction to V_ϕ due to hydrolysis of electrolytes only may be negligible, since the strong hydrogen bonding⁴ between THF and H_2O will reduce the hydrolysis of these electrolytes by free water molecules considerably.

Application of the Redlich-Meyer equation was not possible due to the lack of data on the compressibility and pressure variation of dielectric constant, necessary to calculate the theoretical limiting slope (S_v^*). Thus, the limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0) and experimental slope (S_v^*) were obtained by a least-square method. Within experimental error, values for (V_ϕ^0) varied linearly with \sqrt{c} to follow the following equation⁵,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v^*\sqrt{c} \quad (2)$$

Where S_v^* is a constant, dependent on charge and salt type and can be related to solute-solute interactions and V_ϕ^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume which is related to solute-solvent interactions. The V_ϕ^0 values along with the experimental slopes (S_v^*) are listed in Table 2.

Table 1. Physical properties of pure tetrahydrofuran (THF) and 20 mass% THF + H_2O solvent mixture at different temperatures

T/K	Mass%	$\rho_0/\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$		η_0/cP	
		Present work	Lit.	Present work	Lit.
298	100 (Pure THF)	0.88072	0.88072 ^a 0.88070 ^b	0.46300	0.46300 ^a 0.46000 ^b
303	"	0.87595	–	0.44536	–
308	"	0.87116	0.87116 ^a	0.42770	0.42770 ^a
313	"	0.86627	–	0.40893	–
318	"	0.86140	0.86140 ^a	0.39017	0.39017 ^a
323	"	0.86051	0.86051 ^a	0.38921	0.38921 ^a
298	20	0.98668	0.98668 ^a	1.49002	1.49002 ^a
303	"	0.98488	–	1.31155	–
308	"	0.98309	0.98309 ^a	1.13310	1.13310 ^a
313	"	0.98019	–	1.05991	–
318	"	0.97730	0.97730 ^a	0.89670	0.89670 ^a
323	"	0.97631	0.97631 ^a	0.89535	0.89535 ^a

^aRefs. 1-4, ^bRef. 16.

The variation of V_ϕ^0 with temperature of the electrolytes in this solvent mixture follows the polynomial equation,

$$V_\phi^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (3)$$

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slopes (S_V^*) together with standard errors of different salts in 20 mass% tetrahydrofuran + water at different temperatures

Salts	V_{ϕ}^0 at various temp. ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)					S_V^* at various temp. ($\text{L}^{1/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$)				
	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K	323 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K	323 K
NH_4NO_3	0.933 (± 0.2)	9.157 (± 0.5)	17.115 (± 0.3)	19.751 (± 0.2)	21.062 (± 0.5)	76.239 (± 0.6)	75.378 (± 0.6)	70.059 (± 0.8)	67.603 (± 0.3)	65.715 (± 0.2)
KNO_3	4.731 (± 0.4)	16.532 (± 0.3)	20.726 (± 0.4)	23.049 (± 0.4)	26.155 (± 0.1)	62.311 (± 0.8)	41.510 (± 0.2)	39.029 (± 0.2)	37.668 (± 0.1)	35.437 (± 0.1)
$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.746 (± 0.3)	7.019 (± 0.4)	14.771 (± 0.5)	21.310 (± 0.4)	26.293 (± 0.1)	242.21 (± 0.1)	237.87 (± 0.2)	226.18 (± 0.3)	219.42 (± 0.2)	214.52 (± 0.1)
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	44.297 (± 0.5)	50.449 (± 0.4)	57.154 (± 0.4)	61.684 (± 0.7)	67.329 (± 0.5)	221.71 (± 0.5)	219.59 (± 0.7)	214.54 (± 0.5)	208.17 (± 0.1)	200.54 (± 0.6)

Values in the parenthesis are standard errors.

where T is the temperature in Kelvin. The coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 are determined and the following equations are obtained,

$$V_{\phi}^0/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} = -6477.95/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} + 40.70 T/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1} - 0.063 T^2/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$$

for ammonium nitrate (4)

$$V_{\phi}^0/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} = -5506.53/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} + 34.25 T/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1} - 0.053 T^2/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$$

for potassium nitrate (5)

$$V_{\phi}^0/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} = -105.71/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} + 5.93 T/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1} - 0.007 T^2/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$$

for calcium nitrate (6)

$$V_{\phi}^0/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} = -1578.27/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} + 9.29 T/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1} - 0.013 T^2/\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$$

for magnesium nitrate (7)

The apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) can be obtained by differentiating equation (3) with respect to temperature

$$\phi_E^0 = (\delta V_{\phi}^0/\delta T)_{\rho} = a_1 + 2a_2 T \quad (8)$$

The ϕ_E^0 values of the studied electrolytes at 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K are determined and recorded in Table 3.

The viscosity data of solutions for various electrolytes viz. ammonium nitrate, potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate

and calcium nitrate, in 20 mass% THF + H_2O mixture have been analyzed using the Jones-Dole⁶ equation,

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc \quad (9)$$

$$(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{c} = A + B\sqrt{c}$$

where $\eta = (Kt - L/t) \times \rho$

where η_0 and η are the viscosities of the solvent-mixture and solution respectively, A and B are constants, ρ is the density of the solvent-mixture and K and L are constants for a particular viscometer. The value of A and B are estimated by least-squares method and recorded in Table 4.

Adiabatic compressibility coefficients, β were derived from the relation,

$$\beta = 1/u^2 \rho \quad (10)$$

where ρ is the solution density and u is the sound velocity in the solution. The apparent molal adiabatic compressibility (ϕ_K) of the liquid solutions was calculated from the relation,

$$\phi_K = M/\rho_0 + 1000 (\beta\rho_0 - \beta_0\rho)/m\rho\rho_0 \quad (11)$$

The limiting apparent molal adiabatic compressibilities (ϕ_K^0) were obtained by extrapolating the plots of ϕ_K versus the square root of molal concentration of the solute to zero concentration by the computerised least-squares method,

$$\phi_K = \phi_K^0 + S_K^* m^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

The values of β , ϕ_K , ϕ_K^0 and S_K^* are reported in Table 5.

The S_V^* values shown in Table 2 are positive for all metal nitrates studied here in 20 mass% THF + H_2O mixture indicating strong solute-solute interactions in this mixture medium. This type of behaviour of alkali metal chlorides, tetraalkylammonium halides and some common salts has also been observed in different solvents and solvent-mixtures systems⁷⁻⁹. The possible explanation for the positive slopes in the studied solvent-mixture may be that ionic association

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) for various salts in 20 mass% tetrahydrofuran + water at different temperatures

Electrolytes	Limiting apparent molar expansibilities ϕ_E^0 ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$)				
	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K	323 K
NH_4NO_3	2.292	1.662	1.032	0.402	-0.228
KNO_3	2.130	1.600	1.070	0.540	0.010
$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.387	1.312	1.237	1.162	1.087
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.416	1.286	1.156	1.026	0.896

Table 4. Molar concentrations, densities, viscosities, apparent molar volumes and values of *B*-coefficient and *A* in 20 mass% tetrahydrofuran + water mixture at different temperatures

$c/\text{mol dm}^{-3}$	$\rho_0/\text{g.cm}^{-3}$	η_0/cP	$V_\phi/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$B/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$A/\text{cm}^{3/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2}$
T = 303 K					
NH ₄ NO ₃					
0.03601	0.98719	1.01332	16.009		
0.07801	0.98952	0.91590	20.887		
0.12002	0.99143	0.92989	25.887	2.627	-1.744
0.16203	0.99299	0.94730	30.445	(±0.2)	(±0.3)
0.19083	0.99325	0.98824	35.404		
KNO ₃					
0.03612	0.98791	0.99892	17.487		
0.07825	0.99117	0.92404	21.076		
0.12039	0.99398	0.92845	25.906	2.786	-1.805
0.16253	0.99656	0.94908	29.321	(±0.1)	(±0.2)
0.18841	0.99782	0.98214	32.928		
Ca(NO ₃) ₂					
0.03845	0.99203	1.00406	50.998		
0.08333	0.99881	0.96954	69.998		
0.12820	1.00413	0.96404	87.314	2.842	-1.744
0.17307	0.99858	1.00372	109.534	(±0.1)	(±0.1)
0.20640	1.01033	1.04275	114.578		
Mg(NO ₃) ₂					
0.03862	0.99141	0.94475	88.765		
0.08369	0.99741	0.90561	108.328		
0.12876	1.00248	0.91895	121.564	3.755	-2.164
0.17383	1.00602	0.97568	136.866	(±0.2)	(±0.2)
0.20602	1.00802	1.05038	146.302		
T = 308 K					
NH ₄ NO ₃					
0.03593	0.98512	0.86371	23.889		
0.07781	0.98702	0.79055	29.986		
0.11961	0.98860	0.79783	34.558	2.629	-1.775
0.16159	0.98984	0.80516	38.926	(±0.2)	(±0.3)
0.19029	0.99028	0.82720	42.992		
KNO ₃					
0.03604	0.98586	0.86044	24.767		
0.07798	0.98883	0.79626	28.017		
0.12021	0.99165	0.79833	30.455	2.827	-1.825
0.16215	0.99428	0.81730	32.651	(±0.1)	(±0.2)
0.18798	0.99554	0.84815	35.479		
Ca(NO ₃) ₂					
0.03823	0.99005	0.87511	55.067		
0.08311	0.99668	0.84673	73.867		
0.12747	1.00180	0.84938	90.876	2.994	-1.750
0.17268	1.00593	0.89725	105.653	(±0.2)	(±0.3)
0.20595	1.00815	0.93424	116.438		

Table-4 (contd.)

			Mg(NO ₃) ₂			
0.03851	0.98960	0.79941	95.324			
0.08352	0.99533	0.73764	111.747			
0.12843	0.99973	0.77527	129.032	3.888		-2.286
0.17333	1.00377	0.82594	134.453	(±0.2)		(±0.1)
0.20577	1.00490	0.86226	152.986			
			T = 313 K			
			NH ₄ NO ₃			
0.03584	0.98198	0.76496	30.564			
0.07750	0.98359	0.70052	36.893			
0.11913	0.98501	0.69735	40.365	2.631		-1.818
0.16096	0.98596	0.69509	45.086	(±0.3)		(±0.2)
0.18947	0.98640	0.72982	48.220			
			KNO ₃			
0.03599	0.98281	0.76737	28.777			
0.07786	0.98569	0.70947	31.098			
0.11981	0.98838	0.70972	33.376	2.861		-1.849
0.16166	0.99078	0.72696	36.324	(±0.1)		(±0.1)
0.18730	0.99207	0.75573	38.444			
			Ca(NO ₃) ₂			
0.03809	0.98692	0.78333	60.563			
0.08292	0.99344	0.82371	77.956			
0.12711	0.99843	0.83728	94.554	3.492		-1.769
0.17223	1.00261	0.87629	108.089	(±0.2)		(±0.2)
0.20548	1.00475	0.90497	118.998			
			Mg(NO ₃) ₂			
0.03845	0.98621	0.71287	101.756			
0.08336	0.99208	0.64351	116.098			
0.12818	0.99639	0.68470	132.645	3.955		-1.335
0.17304	0.99987	0.72788	145.543	(±0.1)		(±0.1)
0.20540	1.00124	0.77054	157.032			
			T = 318 K			
			NH ₄ NO ₃			
0.03576	0.97901	0.66412	32.981			
0.07731	0.98062	0.61610	38.001			
0.11873	0.98180	0.61585	43.099	2.872		-1.916
0.16055	0.98293	0.61252	46.008	(±0.2)		(±0.3)
0.18913	0.98319	0.64157	50.032			
			KNO ₃			
0.03582	0.97985	0.67594	30.555			
0.07768	0.98263	0.62620	33.221			
0.11949	0.98520	0.62569	35.777	2.880		-1.862
0.16148	0.98768	0.64070	37.676	(±0.2)		(±0.2)
0.18712	0.98889	0.66384	40.099			
			Ca(NO ₃) ₂			
0.03795	0.98382	0.64805	65.876			

Table-4 (contd.)

0.08244	0.99017	0.66379	81.897		
0.12656	0.99508	0.68592	97.911	4.086	-2.158
0.17130	0.99867	0.70403	113.978	(±0.2)	(±0.1)
0.20494	1.00149	0.76626	120.844		
			Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
0.03827	0.98319	0.62645	104.777		
0.08323	0.98892	0.56411	119.543		
0.12801	0.99336	0.59812	134.021	3.990	-2.364
0.17276	0.99677	0.63586	147.022	(±0.3)	(±0.2)
0.20510	0.99800	0.67741	159.118		
			T = 323 K		
			NH ₄ NO ₃		
0.03565	0.97448	0.59991	33.785		
0.07722	0.97605	0.58833	39.067		
0.11860	0.97728	0.60955	43.423	3.933	-1.937
0.16030	0.97830	0.65284	46.999	(±0.1)	(±0.2)
0.18889	0.97869	0.70751	50.209		
			KNO ₃		
0.03581	0.97526	0.60649	33.312		
0.07732	0.97794	0.58776	35.555		
0.11939	0.98045	0.61386	38.045	3.853	-1.893
0.16134	0.98282	0.65285	40.111	(±0.2)	(±0.3)
0.18706	0.98405	0.71605	42.119		
			Ca(NO ₃) ₂		
0.03782	0.97916	0.57644	69.987		
0.08242	0.98544	0.56608	85.118		
0.12636	0.99016	0.59773	101.543	4.468	-2.192
0.17068	0.99384	0.65358	116.045	(±0.1)	(±0.2)
0.20455	0.99643	0.72632	123.978		
			Mg(NO ₃) ₂		
0.03825	0.97856	0.56695	108.671		
0.08312	0.98410	0.54860	123.855		
0.12794	0.98865	0.58493	136.231	4.955	-2.378
0.17209	0.99202	0.66867	148.776	(±0.1)	(±0.1)
0.20459	0.99306	0.74379	161.787		

Values in the parenthesis are standard errors.

would become quite appreciable in this medium as the concentration of the electrolyte is increased thereby weakening the solute-solvent interactions. As a consequence, contraction of the solvent-mixture would be gradually lowered with increasing concentration of the electrolyte, resulting in a net positive volume change per mole of the added solute. As expected, the S_V^* values decrease with increasing temperature in this solvent mixture for the studied electrolytes, which is attributed to more violent thermal

agitation at higher temperature resulting in diminishing the force of solute-solute interactions (ionic dissociation)¹⁰.

To examine the solute-solvent interactions, the V_ϕ^0 values can be used. Table 2 reveals that V_ϕ^0 values are negative and increase with increasing temperature. This indicates the presence of weak solute-solvent interaction and the solvent molecules are loosely attached to solute which expands with increase in temperature, thus resulting in higher values of V_ϕ^0 at higher temperature in this solvent mixture system.

observed that the values of $(\delta^2 V_\phi^0 / \delta T^2)_p$ for solutions of all electrolytes are negative indicating the structure-breaking behaviour of these electrolytes viz. Ammonium nitrate, potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate in this solvent-mixture.

The molar concentrations (c), densities (ρ), viscosities (η), apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) and values of A and B are recorded in Table 4.

A perusal of Table 4 shows that the values of B -coefficients for all studied electrolytes are positive and large and these values increase with increasing temperature. This indicates that these electrolytes, NH_4NO_3 , KNO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ act as structure-breaker in this solvent-mixture. A similar result was reported by other workers¹² in the case of viscosities of perchlorate of lithium and sodium in propionic acid + ethanol mixture.

It has been reported by a number of workers that dB/dT is a better criterion^{13,14} for determining the structure-making/breaking nature of any electrolyte rather than simply the B -coefficient. It is evident from Table 2 that the values of B are positive and increase with rise in temperature (positive dB/dT) suggesting structure-breaking tendencies of all electrolytes in this mixed solvent system. These conclusions are in excellent agreement with that drawn from $(\delta^2 V_\phi^0 / \delta T^2)_p$ illustrated earlier.

It is seen from Table 5 that all the salts studied here have negative apparent molal adiabatic compressibilities, ϕ_K^0 which become more negative on increasing the temperature. Negative ϕ_K^0 values of the salts are interpreted in terms of the loss of compressibility of THF + water mixture due to electrostrictive forces in the vicinity of the ions. On rising the temperature of the system, the metal ions lose some solvent molecules from their first coordination sphere in a process which is expected to increase the compressibility. But at higher temperature, breakdown of the intermolecular hydrogen-bonds in the THF + water mixed system also takes place more effectively resulting in a loss of compressibility. Thus it may be concluded that for the salts solutions under study, the later effect is growing faster and overriding the former as far as the present temperature range is concerned. From Table 5, it is also evident that limiting experimental slopes, S_K^* have positive values indicating the existence of strong solute-solute interactions in the studied solvent system which resembles the agreement drawn from S_V^* discussed earlier. A similar result was reported by worker¹⁵ in the case of ultrasonic studies of some alkali metal chlorides and bromides in THF + water mixture.

Experimental

The purification of tetrahydrofuran (Merck, India), ammonium nitrate, potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate (AR Sd. fine chemicals) and density measurements of various solutions are described earlier¹⁶. The binary aqueous solutions of tetrahydrofuran as well as the solutions of nitrates were made by mass and conversion of molality into molarity was done¹⁷.

The viscosities were measured by means of suspended-level Ubbelohde¹⁸ viscometer at the desired temperature (accuracy ± 0.01 K). The precision of the viscosity measurements was 0.05%. Details have been described earlier².

Sound velocities were determined with an accuracy of 0.3% using a single crystal variable-path ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, India) working at 4 MHz, which was calibrated with water, methanol and benzene at each temperature. The temperature stability was maintained within ± 0.01 K by circulating thermostated water around the cell by a circulating pump.

The experimental values of densities (ρ_0) and viscosities (η_0) of pure tetrahydrofuran and 20 mass% tetrahydrofuran + water mixture at 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K are recorded (Table 1).

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